

Ambivalence: Towards a New Understanding of Urban Strain

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0 Introduction

Cases of strifes in cities abound. Many consider conflicts a regular, if not symptomatic, feature of urban life. Characteristically, conflicts are classified as expressions of social strains that arise from societal frictions. Conflicts are seen as core features of longer-term processes, considered either as a driving force or as a result of persisting disagreements and altercations. The effects of conflicts on cities tend to be perceived as disruptions or disturbances of the balance of the rhythm of urban life, or in other words, of 'urbanity' as the articulation of a balanced urban culture. While these assessments seem convincing, adopting such perspectives risks overlooking a deeper tension in the background of many urban conflicts. We here propose to dwell on urban conflicts as not necessarily only contingent issues but to consider a *problématique* behind urban conflicts that seems genuinely connected to urbanity in its different shapes. We claim that one can detect a *core ambivalence* of urbanity across socio-cultural contexts.

When using the term 'urbanity' we refer to an urban way of life. We conceive of an urban way of life as interplay of urban practices, discourses and spatially anchored material and social arrangements. This includes ideas, mental images, representations, narratives and symbols of 'the urban' and emphasizes the self-interpretations of the respective social actors in different epochs and regions. The term is meant also to relate to the institutions and agents that seek to ensure an urban character of social life. Notions of urbanity migrate with the historical actors carrying them. In this sense, urban ways of life are found where those enacting them are located, regardless of whether they live in or outside the city. They can orient their way of life to the city – or alternatively reject an urban way of life categorically.

What we argue for in this article has been developed deductively over a long-term engagement with modes of urbanity in various social and historical contexts. By introducing the concept of a core ambivalence of urbanity we want to call attention to a central dimension of urban life without claiming that this would exhaust the idea of urbanity or the conflicts encountered in urban lifeworlds. Our diagnosis does not apply to all forms of urban strain. We rather claim that we can identify a specific *différence* of the urban that can be traced across times and socio-cultural spaces. This *différence* concerns the entrenchment of city dwellers in urban life and affects the collective identity, or the imagined identity, of a city. Focusing on this specific urban *différence* does not pass over

the otherwise huge differences that exist between modes of urbanity in different types of cities. On the contrary, we think that identifying this core difference of urbanity allows for a new, improved strategy of comparison. It allows a mode of comparison that does not impose a vacuous notional *tertium comparationis* on highly different contexts but rather allows following the diverse trajectories of a *problématique* that cities in general face, and thus helps increasing sensitivity for socio-cultural differences of the lives of cities.

To sharpen the concept of ambivalence, we take our inspiration from the observation of several constitutive tensions within urban ways of life that we propose to summarize as 'urban ambivalences'. Employing the concept of ambivalence – in difference to diffusionism, historical dialectics, development, evolution or progress – means to reflect the potential simultaneity of two (or more) tendencies that lead to states of tension with different subsequent effects. These tensions can swing in one direction or the other, they can subside, or they can reinforce each other. The concept of ambivalence stresses constitutive tensions and the bi-valence or bi-polarity of individual and social states, resulting in strain and conflict. The opposition integral to an ambivalent constellation cannot be resolved. Such ambivalences cannot be taken as ephemeral or transitory. When using the concept of ambivalence in research on cities, and on urbanity more particularly, complexity is predicted as condition for the continued existence of a city and an urban way of life. Urban ambivalence has consequences for the spatialization, the social constellations and the relationships between individuals in cities. Focusing on ambivalence is a deeply normative methodological decision but seems a requisite one.

1 Reading cities and urban change in the light of diagnoses of ambivalence and ambiguity

Theorizing of life in modern, contemporary cities (and even more so in attempts to theorize *the city*) has been characterized by identifying constitutive tensions or even opposition right from the start in the early twentieth century. German sociologist Georg Simmel took his starting point from the fundamental tension between the collective and the individual. It is in the necessity of coordinating the myriad movements and activities of the city (Simmel focused, as the title indicates, on *Großstädte*) that this tension is enormously intensified (Simmel 1908). Flooded by innumerable impressions, the

individual needs to reduce affective involvement. It is a seemingly arrogant attitude of disinvolvement (*Blasiertheit*) that Simmel identified as a widespread reaction by those living in big cities. It takes the form of reservation against other individuals, not least in large cities fed by distrust against the hardly known others. This dissociation was, however, not seen as the breakdown of socialising but its specific urban form within an ever larger ensemble of people. This social tension is paralleled by a cultural one. It is in the big cities that the commodification (in material forms invading every household) and the institutionalization of the “spirit” proliferates in an “objectified” form. This *objektive Geist* dwarfs any individual brain. The reaction is a conscious development of individual particularities to defend one’s individuality. This also helps to display a personal profile (not Simmel’s words) easily recognizable even in short social encounters. In that way, equality and utter distinctiveness coexist.

It is such constitutive but likewise historically contingent tensions of the big cities of the early twentieth century that pervaded the thinking of the Chicago School of urban studies, focusing on contemporary American cities instead of Simmel’s Berlin. Yet, where Simmel had focused on the modern *Großstadt*, city, as something radically new (excluding both ancient metropolises and contemporary *Kleinstädte*, small towns), Robert Park and his colleagues took a wider, anthropological perspective (Park et al. 1925, 1-3). The starting point (and the reference to Oswald Spengler) suggests an organicist image of a city characterized by well organised division of labour. Yet in the end, a tension comes to the fore which is produced by the necessity of competition and of communication at the same time.

Louis Wirth defined tensions in a more precise manner. Urban theory takes the city as being defined by its high number of inhabitants and the density of their living together (Wirth 1938). This leads (and we feel reminded of Simmel) to a higher reach in terms of contacts with different types of people and groups and hence a changing and insecure status. Heterogeneity is experienced and adapted to by being a cultured person and a cosmopolite. It is not reduced into a single hierarchy. Yet, in order to deal with this heterogeneity for economic and political purposes, it is necessary to level people, that is to treat them in a typified way. Wirth assumed that the urbanites reacted by trying to form secondary groups based on like interests. Yet, in order to be efficient, such groups need to take the form of organizations. Communication is typified in their media as well as references. Such tensions are open-ended and a continuing task for urban sociology.

In his long-term perspective on urbanism, Richard Sennett identifies a tension between the development of an ever more neutral city, symbolized by the geometric figure of the grid, and the necessity to preserve humanity under such conditions (Sennett 1990). The necessary answer under such conditions is twofold. On the one hand, aesthetic and artistic articulation allows to stress differences. On the other, one needs to give up oneself to such products of others in order to create relations.

Further diagnoses might be added. Spatially, urban agents are torn between *topophilia* and *heterophilia*, between focusing and relating to one's current location and what is associated with it on the one hand and the interest in connectivity beyond the city boundaries, in the distant and including the world in one's city (Bloomfield 2006). There is a constitutive tension between formal and informal economy in successful urbanisation (López 2020: "dual urbanism"). Saskia Sassen's concept of "global cities" has drawn attention to the role played by (in particular, large) cities to create global connections by stressing at the same time, how much local, cheap, and even manual labour forms the basis of the transactional networks of, for instance, financing and communication (Sassen 1991, 2013; for an application e.g. Stahre 2004). Even for Religious Studies this has led to a growing focus on the few, even if growing number of, megacities (e.g. Becci and Burchardt 2013) rather than a broader inquiry into fundamentals of urbanism or, as we prefer to specify, "urbanity" (Rau 2020; Rau and Rüpke 2020; Christ et al. 2023).

Constitutive tensions were not restricted to contemporary "global cities". Even in ancient cities, in Mesopotamia or around the Mediterranean Sea, such tensions can be observed for instance on the social level. Here too, inclusion is in opposition to exclusion, that is, a tension exists between local rootedness, on the one hand, and the wish to extend networks and to travel, on the other (e.g. Goodman 2007; Algaze 2008; Veenhof 2010; Creekmore and Fisher 2014; Rüpke and Urciuoli 2023). Mesopotamian, Graeco-Roman, and Mesoamerican cities frequently had colonies or trading posts in distant settlements. Building walls was often remembered by city-dwellers as an indication of urbanity, yet chronologically often much delayed or not adapted to subsequent growth; urban historiography and sociology long assumed that it went hand in hand with city status. Being granted and performing citizenship differed widely in its inclusion of small or large parts of the dwelling population.

Across periods and regions the urban shares an inclination towards similarity, which is accompanied by an interest in standardisation and effective administration and

manageability. This is in tension with an inclination towards diversity, which focuses on complex division of labour and creativity. The complexity of urbanity reaches from connotations of moral order, through the necessity of politeness or friendliness and class consciousness for peaceful coexistence, to the differentiation and diversity of the inhabitants and their life practices caused by densification processes (as Berking and Löw 2008 suggest). This complexity also includes the view of the inhabitants beyond their own city. All of this, as we are proposing in this article, can be seen as constitutive of the ambivalences of urban socio-spatial relations and (lasting and larger) urban configurations. It depicts a field of constitutive tensions that can be examined in terms of actors, positions, strategies and phenomena, and permits building on and transcending the observations sketched so far.

2 Opting for ambivalence

2.1 The history of the concept of ambivalence

Admittedly, there are other concepts catching constitutive tensions. In philosophical thinking about space, the concept of a polarity between the human subject in its corporeality as an “interior” (*Innen*) and space as the second pole designated as “exterior” (*Außen*) has been invoked. This ontological tension connects both and creates a unit that can be experienced (summarily Gosztanyi 1976, 973). In difference to ambivalence, however, the concept of polarity stresses the unity of an experience, even if it allows for switching a temporary focus to the one or the other pole. This is, why we opt for ambivalence and take up several of the lines that have been developed more recently and try to develop them in a more systematic manner. Thus, we acknowledge the conceptual advances in some recent studies but do not agree with diagnoses of whole periods as being characterized by ambivalence or the absence of it. Instead, we propose to use ambivalence as a concept that helps to better catch the dynamics of growing and diminishing tensions in specific spatio-temporal settings.

As the sketch from the field of urban studies and religious studies shows, ambivalence is not a completely unknown concept. In any case, it could be well integrated into the discourses of the last approximately 100 years. Since the term has actually already been used as a concept of analysis in other research contexts, a brief overview will be given

below. In principle, it is also useful to distinguish ambivalence¹ from ambiguity² (as polysemy, uncertainty), although the terms are sometimes used synonymously in everyday life. According to etymological research, the term first appeared around 1900 and was introduced into scientific language by *psychiatrists* (Eugen Bleuler, Sigmund Freud) to describe the coexistence of opposing feelings in people as “affective ambivalence” (Bleuler 1914). It is probably more than a coincidence that this happened in the same decade as Simmel’s analyses of the mindset of modern city dwellers.

To this day, ambivalence is a concept in *social psychology* (Jonas and Ziegler 2007), but also in musicology, for example when the ambivalence of tonality in the work of Arnold Schönberg is examined (Luchterhandt 2008). *Literature and cultural studies* scholars examine perceptions of ambivalence in literary texts or in photographs and postcards – then they even speak of “ambivalent images” (Junge et al. 2013; Onken 2016). Ambivalence is often not applied as an analytical term in cultural studies, but is used in the sense of double meaning of a situation, thus basically corresponding to what is also understood by ambiguity (see above). This is different in the new book by the historian Hillard von Thiessen, who employs the concept of ambiguity – i.e. not ambivalence! – as an epochal ‘design’ (von Thiessen 2021). Ambiguity, however, is used by von Thiessen less to describe a structural feature of an entire epoch than as a kind of meta-concept, or at least an alternative to the concepts of process of the early modern period such as rationalisation, secularisation, nationalisation or individualisation, which have been discussed for a long time but are often presented in too linear a way. His analytical model is embedded in another concept, that of norm competitions (*Normenkonkurrenzen*), produced by the emergence of competing norm systems in the early modern period (honour, common good and faith) which consequently generated competing expectations of behaviour. The explanatory model is very well suited to explain how people in the early

¹ On the etymology of the term, see the entry in DWDS (*Digitales Wörterbuch der deutschen Sprache*): “Ambivalenz f. ‘Doppelwertigkeit von Gefühlen’, gelehrte Neubildung (1910/11) des Psychiaters E. Bleuler, der unter affektiver Ambivalenz das ‘Nebeneinanderbestehen von entgegengesetzten Gefühlen’ (Zu- und Abneigung zugleich) versteht. Das Wort ist wahrscheinlich nach dem Vorbild von Äquivalenz (s. d.) gebildet aus Valenz (s. d.) in Verbindung mit lat. amb(i)- (s. Ambiguität). – ambivalent Adj. ‘doppelwertig (von Gefühlen), zwiespältig’ (Freud 1916), in der Sprachwissenschaft ‘doppel-, mehrdeutig’ (2. Hälfte 20. Jh.)“ <https://www.dwds.de/wb/Ambivalenz> (1.8.2023), that is “Ambivalence, n. “Duality of feelings”, a scholarly neologism (1910/11) coined by psychiatrist E. Bleuler, who understood affective ambivalence to mean the simultaneous existence of opposing feelings (attraction and repulsion at the same time). The word was probably formed on the model of equivalence from valence in conjunction with Latin amb(i)- (see ambiguity). – ambivalent adj. dual in value (of feelings), two-faced (Freud 1916), in linguistics ‘double, multiple meaning’ (2nd half of the 20th century). – Interestingly the English term is borrowed from German: <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/ambivalence#dictionary-entry-1>

² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/ambiguity>

modern period learned to deal with normative ambiguities, how they could potentially perhaps even practise tolerance of ambiguity unintentionally. For the area of longer-term developments, von Thiessen's book owes readers an explanation, which is perhaps due to his fundamentally dismissive attitude towards linearity. One can only imagine the longer-term perspective, the progression of history, as the sum of many ambiguities that at some point perhaps led to some kind of reversal. However, such longer-term developments could also be integrated by adding a level of the observer. Although von Thiessen works with the concept of ambiguity rather than ambivalence, he has shown the value of applying such a concept to earlier epochs when the word as such did not yet exist. On a wider scale one can discern a shift from demonising ambivalence to recognising and even praising it after the postmodern intervention.

In a similar manner, *social theorist* Peter Wagner, inspired by Max Weber and Cornelius Castoriadis, regards ambivalence as feature characteristic of an epoch, in this case modernity. For him modernity is characterized by a structural ambivalence on the level of the guiding imaginary significations, between the two ideas of human – individual and collective – ‘autonomy’ (and self-determination) and ‘unlimited’ instrumental-rational ‘mastery’ (and control) of the world, resulting in continuing contestations (Wagner 2001, 18, 24, et passim).

In *Classical sociology*, Robert Merton and Elinor Barber in their programmatic 1963 article (reprint, Merton and Barber 1976) introduced the notion of “sociological ambivalence” as a “major source” of psychological ambivalence (7). At the core, or what they call the “restricted sense”, sociological ambivalences refer to “incompatible” normative expectations “inherent” in (the definition of) social roles or statuses, or as “embedded” in statuses (7), and to the conflicts these entail. In an extended sense they apply the term ambivalences to all incompatible normative expectations. In this context, Merton and Barber in some sections try to introduce a hierarchy between lead or “major” norms and “minor counter-norms” (17). They seek the “structural” sources for these ambivalences in the discrepant “attributions” others make regarding the occupants of particular roles. By extension, Merton in a separate article of the same year sees social institutions themselves patterned by “conflicting pairs of norms” and applies the term ambivalence for these conflicting pairs too (Merton 1976). Barber's and Merton's conception tries to overcome the individualized, personalized understanding of ambivalence, but their conceptualization of ambivalence remains insufficiently relational.

Differently, the *postmodernist sociologist* Zygmunt Bauman (1991) broadens the scope of ambivalence and turns ambivalence into a key concept of critical societal theory (*Gesellschaftstheorie*). Modernity at its core – Bauman only thinks of Western modernity – means for Bauman a “struggle for order” against ambivalence (1991, 6, 24): “modern times” represent “an era of particularly bitter and relentless war against ambivalence” and “uncertainty” (1991, 3, 242). For him it is “situations” and “conditions” in which people are caught – conditions of “indeterminacy” and “fuzziness” – that appear as ambivalent and against which the modern “ambivalence-eliminating project” is pitched (1991, 2, 7, 9); on the cultural level this is related to a specific mode of social “consciousness” and gets reflected in social values (1991, 2, 75, 98). Significantly, Bauman conflates at several instances in his argument ambivalence and ambiguity (1991, 6-7). Postmodernity then means “emancipation from the characteristically modern urge to overcome ambivalence” and from the values central to uniformity as well as universalism (98). Being lifted from a subjectivist to a social characteristic, ambivalence turns in Bauman’s hands into something valuable, something normatively appreciated in postmodern Western contexts.

The plea for ambivalence as a social value in postmodern thinking goes back, on the one hand, to a diagnosis of the present: more and more people seem to feel and behave ambivalently, seem to feel more comfortable in undecided states than with clear decisions, do not want to resolve contradictions. These are the typical signs of a postmodern society. But a large part of the people cannot cope with them either and therefore long for unambiguity and truth again. Above all, they can express themselves accordingly in the social media. And populist parties thrive on this. On the other hand, affirmative ambivalence is also already expressing itself in a new way of writing history that has no clear beginning and (as yet) no end; which are rather ‘open histories’ that go further and in which those still alive can appear as formative, creative actors. Analogous open histories in past times, for example in situations of threat, are also increasingly being studied (Vester 1997; Plattform Offene-Geschichte.de).

In *postcolonial discourse*, on the contrary, it is the modernist project, of which the colonized are the victims, that produces ambivalence. Ambivalence here does not appear as a desired state, but as a state in which one is trapped, above all the colonial subjects, but in a different way also the colonizers. With respect to the colonial differentiation and discrimination of (and between) cultures, Homi Bhabha (1994, 34) diagnoses ‘the

problem of ambivalence of cultural authority' – 'the attempt to dominate in the name of a cultural supremacy which is itself produced only in the moment of differentiation'. The attempts of disavowal of such difference on the side of the colonized and their 'desire' for being recognized by the colonizers, he sees leading to 'the ambivalence of mimicry', mimicry rearticulating 'presence in terms of its "otherness", that which it disavows', the colonialized Other ending up as a subject 'that is almost the same but not quite', 'almost the same but not white' (1994, 86, 89, 91; cf. Lee 2014, 56; Razinsky 2017, 45-47).

Western philosophy took longest to accept ambivalence as a condition and a concept. Maurice Merleau-Ponty allowed for dealing with ambivalence. Taking Emily Lee (2016) as a guide, Merleau-Ponty, focusing phenomenologically on the psychological dimension and drawing from Melanie Klein's work, contrasted ambivalence and ambiguity: ambivalence is characteristic of "rigid" personalities who tend to perceive the world "dichotomously" (61), it consists in having "two alternative images of the same object, the same person, without making any effort to connect them" (ambivalence of this kind marks a stage in childhood) (59) and makes people "vacillate" between oppositions, whereas ambiguity for Merleau-Ponty means "openness" towards difference, allowing to see that everything has different meanings: "Ambiguity is the ability to see the other in her complexity ..." (58): "Growing out of ambivalence and developing ambiguous ways of being in the world marks maturity" (67). "Ambiguity is ambivalence that one dares to look at face to face" (Merleau-Ponty 1964, 103; quoted by Lee (66)). For Merleau-Ponty ambiguity marks a more mature state than what ambivalence stands for.

Only very recently Western philosophers started engaging with ambivalence itself as something meaningful and fruitful, but again confined the discussion to the subjective level. After the initial postcolonial and postmodernist debates, and against the background of a strong philosophical tradition, which, starting with Plato, regards ambivalence as "a direct threat to well-functioning agency" (Coates 2023, 4), young philosophers like Hili Razinsky (2017) and D. Justin Coates (2023) plead for recognizing ambivalence as core characteristic of human agency and subjectivity. Coates explicitly turns against the ideal of a fully integrated self (or "a fully integrated practical identity") that has guided the major "unificationist" philosophical schools. Instead, he assumes selves and agents as being "fragmented": "the ideal of human agents as unified, perfectly consistent little wholes is itself misguided. It's not just an unachievable ideal; it's also unattractive" (Coates 2023, 196). Only by acknowledging the conflictual nature of

relationships, commitments, concerns, values and norms can “normative competence” be exercised in a full sense (earlier Maurice Merleau-Ponty already saw in acknowledging ambiguity the more mature state). Less emphatically, Razinsky too regards ambivalence as an “ordinary mode of subjectivity” (2017, 4) and conceives of a person as constituting “a unity in plurality” (2017, 67, 134). Razinsky locates ambivalence in a person’s (mental) attitudes, emphasizing their dispositional dimensions (2017, 80-81, 85), and in a wider sense, including people’s actions, in people’s “engagements” (2017, 22, 67, 135, 169).³ She conceives of two ways in which ambivalence can be described, either as “a unitary tension-fraught attitude towards something or someone”, or in terms of having “two opposing attitudes to one and the same thing” (2017, 5, 73). In her view, the condition of ambivalence cannot be overcome: attempting to “solve” one’s ambivalence “would itself be part of an ambivalent path” (2017, 6).

Thinking about ambivalence is not restricted to European traditions of reflection. An important position of *Indian philosophy* starts from the concepts of *syādvāda* and *anekāntavāda*, that is, the concept of manifold co-existing perspectives and of the multi-layered nature of reality (Parson 2019; Banerjee/Nigam/Pandey 2016, 43f). It is not the classical monistic traditions of Indian philosophy (*advaita*), but such concepts, which tolerate ongoing tensions, that have been appealing to postcolonial thinkers.

To sum up this section, for the study of the reciprocal constitution of religion and urbanity, we now propose to use the concept of ambivalence in the sense of a continuous constitutive ambiguity. Such a term stresses conflict and constitutive tensions. Methodologically, it focusses on multi-polar constellations and bi-valence at any given moment. The oppositions thus identified are not predicted to quickly dissolve in a synthesis on the model of thesis and antithesis and dialectical developments thus constituted. What individual historical actor might identify or denounce as good or bad religion, as good or bad urbanity is not predicted to be ephemeral and transitory. Observations in the history of urbanisation as well as the history of religion (on which we shall briefly reflect in the next section) rather suggest that such contradictions do not quickly disappear and dissolve into mono-valence and unambiguity. If at all, they could – temporarily – be removed only by massive force. Despite its precariousness, we thus

³ But avoids including the „with“, the relational dimension, of engagements in her definition.

predict complexity as a condition for survival rather than a critical state. This is a deeply normative methodological decision.

Ambivalence, however, is not just a potential property of complex systems. Above all, its origins in psychological research invites to apply it in agent-based analyses as we have proposed them for research into the research objects constituted by the general terms of cities and religion. Ambivalence might be constitutive in many fields. Yet, it seems to be of particular relevance in the fields of Urban Studies and Religious Studies.

2.2 Constitutive tensions in religious practices and beliefs

Religious socio-spatial relations and configurations can likewise be described by ambivalence and has increasingly been described in polar terms. Topologically and spatially relevant ambivalences have been described fruitfully by historian of religion Jonathan Z. Smith. We refer here to his conceptual pair of locative and utopian. Smith introduced, somewhat hesitatingly, these terms in order to differentiate two general orientations (“visions of the world”) seen in religious practices and beliefs (Smith 1978b, 101, orig. 1971). He differentiated what he calls the locative and utopian world-views as follows:

“The former is concerned primarily with the cosmic and social issues of keeping one’s place and reinforcing boundaries. The vision is one of stability and confidence with respect to an essentially fragile cosmos, one that has been reorganized, with effort, out of previous modes of order and one whose ‘appropriate order’ must be maintained through acts of conscious labour. We may term such locative traditions, religions of sanctification. The soteriology of such a view is two-fold: emplacement is the norm, rectification, cleaning or healing is undertaken if the norm (expressed primarily, although not exclusively, in the language of ‘boundaries’) is breached” (Smith 1994, 121).

There is a frequent correlation of widespread political participation with rigid social orders and hierarchies. This goes together with Smith’s observation of a frequent “ideological insistence on a democracy of responsibility for maintaining the proper *loci*” (ibid.). Spatially, the focus is on central place. In terms of agent, such a worldview does not exclude religious agents, who carefully explore factual differences of reality and norms (or expectations) and professionalize such roles for instance as diviners entertaining and displaying “confidence in the possibility of rectification” (ibid., 136). The alternative, a utopian understanding, might result from experiences of alienation and resentment (141). The dichotomy of threatened centre and threatening periphery is

replaced by the possibility of rebellion rather than celebration and sanctification and a preference for the non-place, *utopia*; security is now provided by a socio-spatial configuration, that is, a network of like-minded rather than the local political community as such (see Smith 1978a, 186-7).

Against a frequent misinterpretation (anticipated already in Smith's earliest proposal), the "centripetal-closed-locative" and the "centrifugal-open-utopian view" are co-existing modes and not evolutionary steps in a development that changed from the first to the second in (above all Christian) late antique religion (Smith 1978b, 101). Both forms do co-exist and people are moving from one to the other. It is on such phenomena, their agents, and justifications that Smith was interested in rather than in their purely spatial aspects. After all, it was his critique of Mircea Eliade's overemphasis of sacred centres that offered the starting points for his conceptual pair.

It is in a renewed emphasis on the spatiality of religious practices and images that the anthropologist Thomas Tweed developed Smith's distinction. Famous is his pair of "dwelling and crossing" (Tweed 2006). It is building on his studies of pilgrimages of Cubans in exile (Tweed 1997) and shaped by actual religious movements. Religion, or better, religious practices are "confluences of organic-cultural flows that intensify joy and confront suffering by drawing on human and superhuman forces to make homes and cross boundaries" (Tweed 2006, 54). They are complex movements (always including bodies, 61) that provide orientation and establish spatial relationships; Tweed is adamant in the aquatic quality of his metaphors and in the dynamic state of any confluences and "sacrosapes" (54-79; see also Tweed 2020). The "homes" addressed here include not only home and homelands, but also the shared cosmos. Accordingly, the crossings are "terrestrial, corporeal, and cosmic", up to the ultimate horizon (Tweed 2006, 76).

What is most interesting in the heuristic unfolding of Tweed's definition is the co-existence of both directions and the implied tension (which has not been further worked out by Tweed himself). The *and* between dwelling and crossing is inviting to explore how individuals combine both or opt for the one or the other in more or less consistent manners. Systemically, the one cannot exist without the other.

Even less than Jonathan Z. Smith's polar pair, Tweed's bifocal characterization cannot be easily projected onto the topography of a city but fits into the methodological approach to describe the urban by appealing to tensions. For religion, further cases of similar

strategies can be adduced. Jeppe S. Jensen introduced the notion of religion being constituted by the interplay of “i-religion” and “e-religion” (Jensen 2014) but rather in a passing and additive manner of building blocks.

More to the point is the mutual constitution of humans’ “religious” agency and the “divine” agency ascribed to super-human addressees in religious communication (Rüpke 2015, 2018b, 2021). In analysing actions, beliefs, and institutions as religious, the focus is put onto human agents and their acting within frameworks of social constraints and cultural traditions. Invoking transcendent actors and attributing “divine” power to them does not only allow to bolster pre-constituted authority by additional resources. It also enables (in J.Z. Smith’s word) “rebellion” and arrogating agency and authority by redefining more-than-social constellations. Religious action can thus be analysed in its role for processes of traditionalization and community-building as much as de-traditionalization and individualization (Fuchs et al. 2019). Constitutive tensions do not stop here. The very processes of sacralization and de-sacralization or “profanization” of spaces, objects, and relationships and their alternation (cf. Schwerhoff 2008) are early company to the development of religious institutions and concepts of sacrality. This is later developed in the battle-ground of the clearly articulated but rarely unanimously accepted differentiation of the religious and the non-religious (cf. Burchardt, Wohlrab-Sahr, and Middell 2015 and the documentation in Kleine, Wohlrab-Sahr 2024-25) that is kept outside of our analysis.

2.3 Ambivalent urbanity instead of a globally valid definition of city

Having argued for the applicability of ambivalence for that factor in urban developments that we are focusing upon, namely religion, we need to return to *urban* ambivalence and elucidate an important conceptual implication. Thinking about urban ambivalences does not mean that they only exist *in* cities. In fact, there is much to be argued that conflicts and constitutive tensions are more typical of cities than of villages; but they are not limited to cities in the strict sense either. The adjective “urban” allows for that, i.e. for widening the scope beyond the space of the city. For this reason, we decided against a globally valid, uniform definition of the city for the *religion-and-urbanity approach*, which aims to look

at cities from several millennia, spread over several continents. There are simply too many different historical and regional definitions of what a “city” is.

Going beyond the city also means going beyond the city as a material container of built-up infrastructure and architecture. It is not amassed clay, stone, wood and in between streets that makes a city. Rather, cities come into being whenever there is urban life – whenever people decide they’re living in a city that they are shaping and whenever they live a life that to them is consciously distinct from the “rural” life of their neighbours. We call this self-image “urbanity”, seeing it as the precondition of any city. Often mental images, role models and representations of urban ways of life play a role in this, but also the materiality and social practices of people – or rather the interplay of all three. Emphasising the interplay of discourses, materiality and practices in urbanity, and not just the built-up, architectural form of a city, also frees the researcher’s eye to look for and find urban life outside the city, as long as this “outside” still exists.

In both history and the present, we can observe a number of such tensions of urbanity that we can call “urban ambivalences” or “ambivalent urbanities”. However, before we discuss these further, we must first make a basic distinction: that between actor and observer level, analogously between micro and macro level. If we are at the actor level, whether in the past or in the present, we have to ask whether actors can decide at all in a situation of tension, whether they have the necessary power and resources to do so. In most societies, even in participatory democracies, there are groups that cannot decide. The observers, on the other hand, do not have to decide; instead, they observe individuals and groups, reflect and can at best interpret the situation narratively. The macro level is then the highest level of observation at which the decisions of individual actors are no longer of interest. Rather, it is the level at which one sees tensions and stabilisations alternating, where the tensions have dissolved or intensified, where they have stabilised – at least temporarily – or have been transformed into structures or institutions.

Such insights might also guide scholars of religion. Studying religious ambivalences would replace aiming at a definition of religion deduced from the characteristics of “religions” regarded as fixed and coherent packages. This could help to grasp the perspectives of individual actors and processes of dichotomic or temporarily monopolistic stabilisations. In this article, we will, however, focus on the urban side.

3 Ambivalence at the core of urbanity

3.1 Organic unity or diverse conglomeration: the core ambivalence

Putting urbanity at the centre allows for a broader view on cities than with other approaches. Conventional approaches (including urbanization approaches) take the existence of a city as a given and as their starting point, and try to track what happens in a city and to a city. On such line, urbanity would then in the first instance refer to the ways people, residents, live the city and in a city. However, secondarily and in addition, the focus on urbanity opens a wider perspective and allows looking at how the people, residents, inhabitants, relate to “their” city and how they experience and perceive, as well as conceive, their place of residence. We have to distinguish between different kinds of relating to a city (which is being only partially reflected in the different typologies of cities extant). What this gets us to, is a specific way of connecting internal and external views on a city, moving back and forth between the internal and the external views. In important respects, the analytical perspective follows the internal perspectives. At the same time, listening to, or perceiving, subjective perceptions adequately requires a self-critical stance of the analysts who have to overcome inclinations towards a positivist rendering of urban life.

“Members” and inhabitants of a city differ with respect to the degree of anchorage in, and belonging to, their city. *Zugehörigkeit*, the sense of belonging, is not a negligible question for urban studies. Different from rural life and the attachment to ancestral villages, urban residents are often less permanently grounded in a specific city. They may even feel “displaced”. There are regions, for instance in contemporary India, where even long-term urban citizens continue relating to their ancestral villages as their felt home. In other cases, people want to move on, seek to change places, and, in this sense, may relish the possibilities urban life offers, however show only a shallow degree of belonging towards a specific city.

If historians and sociologists state that cities are corporate actors represented by its leaders or governing boards (“city x decided to engage in ...”, “city y pursued the strategy of ...” or “city z was positioned as successful or as disadvantaged at a particular historical juncture”) this would take all other residents as silent members of a city. This way of speaking also treats all cities as if of one kind, namely a particular variety of collective actors. On the other hand, statements of belonging by the inhabitants of a city, giving a particular city as one’s place of residence (or, one of one’s places of residence), can be

either simply factual statements (information on where one currently “resides”), or, alternatively, statements of deeper connectivity to the respective city. Phenomenologically and in the eyes of the inhabitants (as well as many visitors), a town can appear as a unit, with some sense of unity, or, otherwise, as just a conglomerate of physical structures, a site where various actors, interest groups and residents of different standing happen to meet or happen to be concentrated.

A city can thus be viewed as geared towards integration of its members, or as just a crossing point of networks of different kinds and extent (commercial, political, religious, intellectual) and as a meeting point of varied and diverse “communities”. Asking more specifically, what keeps a city together, possible answers are the various webs of interests or even, simply, the urban administration (be it the administration of an empire or a kingdom, the government of a self-ruling city, a pre-modern “state”, or, finally, a nation-state), or the city’s cohesion is borne by its inhabitants (perhaps, in some meaningful sense, incorporated in forms of “self-governance”)? Do inhabitants identify with a city in strong ways? Do they regard a city as “their” city, perhaps expressed through collective rituals or shared stories, narratives and identity discourses? In their most pronounced form, such practices would allow for involvement with designing and developing the city as well as providing possibilities for inhabitants (members) to unfold their individual potentials. Or, do inhabitants, while being physically close to each other, remain “spiritually remote” to one another (to repurpose a statement of Zygmunt Bauman regarding the position of “strangers”; 1991, 60), and, perhaps, identify with just certain aspects of (life in) a city? The last-mentioned option includes the possibility to keep city life, and the collectives that dominate the life of a city, at a distance. The potential of distancing oneself from the hustle and bustle in a city is itself a very urbanist and individualizing life option, much more than what rural life contexts allow for. In a nutshell, are residents of a city “citizens” (as in certain European traditions) or are they simply inhabitants, or, most radically, just subjects (*Untertanen*)? Or do we encounter – differing across types of cities and eras – iridescent, shifting, ambivalent combinations of the different possibilities?⁴ How, and to which degree, do people feel personally as well as

⁴ Prevalence of subjecthood over citizenship (both in the sense of urban belonging and in the sense of membership in the wider society or, in our days, a nation-state) is not a pre-modern phenomenon only, but is being (and again increasingly) met with under modern conditions too, and this not only under authoritarian regimes. More generally, under modern conditions subjecthood shows in form of control of populations (in Foucault’s sense), the alternative being represented by democratic and participatory practices. On the city level these may take the shape of institutionalized urban self-administration or of unruly and unregulated “political society” (Partha Chatterjee 2004), social and political movements, etc.

interpersonally anchored in – or, conversely, feel alienated from, or subjectively distant from – a city? Are some sections of city inhabitants privileged members of the city, citizens in a full sense of the term? Do other sections have a precarious status only, not belonging, and not feeling to belong, to a city completely, sometimes even being only tolerated temporarily and in a subordinate mode?⁵ In which way does one “belong” to a city, how far and how deeply does one belong, in what sense does one have “membership” of a city, as a citizen, as someone with a role or function in a city, or as just someone with a serving or subservient function? Or, does a city just represent one’s place of residence that could also be elsewhere, or that is transient and could be shifted?

Detached belonging, or selective belonging, shows also in another form. Urbanity can refer to a habitus, or a life-style or mode of life, that is only loosely connected to a particular place: cosmopolitan urbanities that allow changing places (cities), and settling in into other places, with relative ease. On a wider scale this can be encountered in today’s world, but historically it had been characteristic of the transcontinental worlds of many intellectuals and, partly, of certain religious actors as well as long-distance merchants (probably already since the bronze age, if not even earlier). Wherever such people settle afresh, often just for a limited time, they relate to other residents, and to urban institutions and spaces, and tend to identify with their cities of residence more selectively than longer-term inhabitants do. Urban residents at the lower end of the social scale, who sometimes are seen today as representing alternative forms of cosmopolitanism, relate to their momentary cities of residence in again different ways: their selective urban connections are often restricted to groups of peers – workers or migrants in similar conditions, or the “communities” of belonging they bring along. Only under specific conditions, like times of social mobilization (for instance in early 20th century Dublin) (O’Reilly, forthcoming), do such urban residents develop connections across neighbourhoods and peer groups on a city-wide scale, or even beyond one city.

We see in the different modalities of relation of inhabitants to cities the core question, or core ambivalence, underlying urbanity, an ambivalence for the inhabitants of a city (the subjective, internal perspective of social actors) as well as for scholarship on urbanity (the analytical perspective of observers). Ambivalence in this case not only concerns the

⁵ Even where one finds early forms of citizenship, like in parts of late medieval and early modern Europe, full *Bürgerstatus* was limited to a small layer of inhabitants, often only 10-20% of the population. On premodern urban citizenship see Prak 2018.

individual person, or a particular group of persons, but applies across all inhabitants of a city – an ambivalence of positionality of people vis-à-vis a place and its other occupants. Talking of “ambivalence” is the analyst’s idiom (even though we are, personally, in our own lives, also part of the field researched). Our claim is that this diagnosis reflects the differences in attitude towards urban life among residents. The task would then be to explore the ways, the forms, and the tensions involved, with which city residents are experiencing and expressing the underlying ambivalence. Our further claim is that this diagnosis is valid across times and spaces, of course taking different shapes and showing in varying degrees.

We thus modify, or develop, the notion of ambivalence. Referring to the ambivalence(s) of urbanity, we continue with the basic understanding by focusing on the ways people, subjects, relate to cities or to urban life, and by extension, how city residents relate to each other. But we also pick on the structural side of urbanity by claiming that a basic ambivalence, together with secondary ambivalences, is an overall characteristic of the ways a city is lived: the ambivalent conditionality of urbanity (*reflected* in the attitudes of urbanites or the ways people relate to a city). We also claim that one can distinguish cities according to the degree and the ways in which they are seen by the residents as a unit(y), and a place of belonging, or as rather places or spaces of pragmatic existence, or even just sites of necessity or need. Cities, in a way, are fragile and precarious entities, even where occupation of a place has continued over long periods of time.

In concurrence with contemporary theoretical deliberations, we regard ambivalence as a condition that persists. While conceived as condition of being torn between opposing, even contradictory perspectives or attitudes, or, as the other option, by a “unitary tension-fraught attitude” (Razinsky 2017), we do not assume that this usually leads to a resolution. With a view to the dynamics induced by the variations in relating to cities, we do not suggest viewing the reality on the ground in a bi-polar fashion, nor do we want to consider the alternatives as the two extremes of a sliding scale. The very fact of ambivalence characterizing urbanity, and the wide array of mixes, combinations and intersections of integration and aloofness, deep belonging and pragmatic attachment, developing out of the basic ambivalence explains the failure of dichotomous models, and of determinate theories of the urban more generally.

3.2 Dimensions of urban ambivalences

The alternatives and possibilities caught by the diagnosis of a core ambivalence inscribed into urbanity regularly find expression in differences of understanding of a particular city, and tensions between different groups or categories of residents in this regard. The layout of a city, at a particular point in time, may even mirror the socio-spatial configuration, namely, the distinction and the tensions between the different residential categories or categories of inhabitants. The ambivalent conditionality of urbanity for a city's residents finds its expression in forms and degrees of belonging and not-belonging, of exclusion and exclusion (in urban life-worlds), being reflected in the attitudinal ambivalences of the residents vis-a-vis a place and its (other) occupants: connectedness (even identification) and distancing (regarding a place and its occupants); participation in, and detachment from, urban life-worlds; togetherness and segregation. Thus a structural and a subjective dimension.

In the following sections we explore the articulations of the core ambivalence in three different directions, reflecting different disciplinary approaches. Our aim is to demonstrate how employing the concept of ambivalence opens up new perspectives on instances or trajectories of urban and religious dynamics. After looking at the formation of socio-economic and socio-cultural dynamics of differentiation (3.2.1) we turn to spatialisations of conflicts (3.2.2) and the urban entanglement of religious individualization and group-formation (3.2.3). We invite readers to identify further dimensions of urban and religious ambivalences and thus sharpen the conceptual tool. This is collective work in progress.

3.2.1 Socio-economic and socio-cultural dynamics of differentiation – intersectional tensions and mediations

The diagnosis of a core ambivalence of urbanity provides a key to capturing people's relationships to a city and helps elucidating the degree to which someone is considered, or feels, to belong to a city. This encompasses the big question of rights to a city (or even to the city in general; Lefebvre 1968), and of the limitation, and even the denial, of rights – the exclusion – of others. It further provides the possibility of tackling constellations in which inhabitants feel alienated from a city. This allows addressing cases in which urban residents show a distancing attitude and have mental reservations regarding city life along with cases in which sections of inhabitants face rejection by others.

The hypothesis of an irreducible core urban ambivalence permits a better understanding of conflicting attitudes vis-à-vis other urban residents – inclinations towards uniformity on the one hand, tolerance, if not celebration, of the heterogeneity of ways of living on the other, or, alternatively, attitudes of simple callousness regarding relationships with other residents. The core ambivalence allows us to ask who has which options in urban life. From the structural angle, the detection of an irreducible core ambivalence of urbanity provides a privileged access to the tensions and conflicting tendencies characteristic of urban life. These comprise policies of homogenisation and endorsements of diversification.

To a certain extent the subjective as well as the structural dimensions of urban ambivalence correlate with the social positionalities and alignments of the various sections of the urban population. Here, the intersectionalities of the different positional factors are of major significance. Centrally important, of course, are the socioeconomic – status and class – differences of inhabitants, which again have to be differentiated along gender lines. Gender distinctions take different forms depending on status, including caste, and class distinctions. In many cases, the socioeconomic status becomes the defining criterion for full acceptance and full-fledged inclusive membership in a city and for admission to the circles epitomizing the commanding form of urbanity that sets the tone at a particular place. The way in which this works depends on the respective socioeconomic formation – the forms of labour extraction and dependency, on the one hand, and the types of businesses on the other – and on the modes of interconnection and interaction, or demarcation, between and across classes or strata. What matters in particular, are the ways in which the dominant and the subaltern groups and strata, as well as intermediate strata, are organized, or else lack consistent forms of organization requiring individuals and households to largely fend for themselves. The strength of urban anchorage, however, is not necessarily congruent with the socioeconomic or class status of a city's inhabitants.

The political and socioeconomic circumstances intersect with other factors – most importantly ethnic, linguistic and religious distinctions, not least also patterns of discrimination of others as “polluting”, especially in South Asia and the South Asian diasporas. They intersect equally with diversities of lifestyle and communal allegiance that may or may not coincide with religious and ethnic affiliations or with status and class

differences respectively. In many cases, not least in our days, ethnic-religious and lifestyle distinctions also entail tensions and conflicts between variant normative orders.

Regarding the dynamics and the sway of urban ambivalences, much depends on the extent to which the different factors converge, overdetermining each other's impact interferentially, or intersect. Politically relevant is whether cultural commonalities have hardened into essentialized identities, self-attributed or ascribed, and in this form become drivers of action. The degree of overlap or congruency of domains and factors has repercussions regarding the strength and size of distinct social units among the urban population and their spatial separation. In cases in which factors do not converge but rather intersect, what to an outsider looks a socioeconomically or religiously circumscribed group or milieu can appear as splintering. The spatial dimension of social segregation is discussed in more detail in the next subchapter.

The effects of the respective modalities of different socioeconomic and sociocultural factors, including the power dynamics involved, and of the scale of their intersectionality range from animosity to indifference up to genuine concern for the fate of the other sections of the population and the other sectors of the city; from the marginalization, segregation, and even exclusion of sections of the urban population to a balanced relationship between social and cultural groups (and individuals) up to a (sometimes patronizing) relationship of social responsibility and support for the disadvantaged sections of a city.

Intersectional animosities and the segregation and marginalization of groups can take the form of conflicts over cultural norms and behavioural ethics. Tensions and animosities between sections of the urban population can escalate into hostilities against groups, and against the residential areas where they are concentrated, and can result in acts of repression and subjugation. Violence can also result when those who feel marginalised assert themselves. Groups may be othered as cultural 'strangers' and can, especially when smaller in size and power, slide into a minority status. People given minority status are not necessarily economically weak, but persecution as minorities may lead to economic marginalization and deterioration.

How tensions are expressed and dealt with, and how conflicts are mitigated, is decisive for the future of a city. The emphasis on urban ambivalence also allows a better understanding of how tensions can be attenuated and conditions stabilized. Cities may have mediating formal structures of governance, or – often being more effective –

informal social self-governance structures that help settle conflicts (e.g. Fuchs 2005 with respect to a district of Mumbai), or cities may feature a ‘cosmopolitan’ self-image (as Mumbai did before 1992; versions of this one can find in other metropolises, both historical and contemporary). This requires an underlying notion of shared ethics of tolerance and of the acceptance of difference and the plurality of worldviews. Attenuation may work for some urban residents, perhaps by way of their spiritual practices or beliefs, and not for others.

Cities can be subject to one overall regulatory order, but there have also been many cases in which different religious, ethnic or professional groups operated by their own regulations in many respects and had their separate self-governance and decision-making bodies and in which the overarching authority had a mediating role at best. Examples would be the medieval and early modern *kontors* – foreign trading posts – of the Hanse in Bergen, Brugge/Bruges, London and Novgorod; of Venetians in early modern Constantinople; of early modern Florentine trading posts in Rome and Lyon; or of Ottoman Tunis up to the mid-nineteenth century (Schubert 2002; Dursteler 2006; Häberlein et al. 2019; Lafi 2005]; ~~trading caste councils in West-Indian cities in pre-colonial times~~).

Finally, putting the focus on the (experience of the) core urban ambivalence allows a better understanding of other conflictual dimensions that deeply affect urbanity. This concerns above all shaky identities and polarised aspirations attributable to external factors. Particularly glaring examples concern the socio-cultural ‘identities’ of many ethnic, religious and socio-economically demarcated groups in colonial and postcolonial countries as well as today’s diasporic urban contexts that appear as acutely unstable, in constant flux and therefore precarious. Many residents of colonized and postcolonial cities have been victims of eviction and forcible resettlement – ‘unrooted’ from often rural and tribal backgrounds or expelled from the cities of their birth. Similarly, there has been a fast rising number of people who were forced to flee to other countries as a result of military campaigns and conflicts, seeking asylum, or have migrated for security reasons or to find a living away from home. In many postcolonial cities the mix of population keeps changing quickly. In all these cases people struggle for a newly affirmed collective identity. We can spot effects of similar disastrous events with comparable consequences in earlier historical periods, especially in cases of aggressive empires, like the Roman, one

particular blatant case being the exodus of the residents of Jerusalem after the destruction of the city in 70 CE.

Aspirationally, under these conditions people often find themselves in a quandary. Meant to adapt to what is considered the exemplary way of (middle-class or mid-range) life, they are often seen as falling short of meeting requirements and social norms, or they are themselves in two minds regarding which socio-cultural model to follow, that which informed their earlier life or that of their new 'home', and feel unable to do full justice to any of them. What had been exemplary life-style models become themselves weakened and torn, become unconvincing and are getting contested, among others by radical alternatives that promise a new holistic life vision. The life perspectives of the resident population, especially of the poorer sections, become upset too in this process. Many local residents feel overrun by rapid global urbanization and rampant gentrification and feel losing their place in the ever more densified cities. The position of more and more city dwellers can thus be regarded as insecure, vulnerable and 'hybrid', being caught between prototypical, increasingly globalized aspirational and occupational models that remain out of reach for many, and region- and 'culture'-specific models and patterns that adapt to, intermix with, or counterpose what seems the socially most prestigious model. All the processes mentioned reinforce the ambivalence of belonging to a city. All the more, cities remain major life anchors.

3.2.2 Spatialisation and temporalisation of conflicts versus deterritorialization of the urban

Alongside the socio-economic and socio-cultural factors that differentiate urban societies, we can also consider the spatial and temporal dimensions of urban differentiation.

For decades, sociology and cultural studies of space have been working with the thesis that social relationships and social processes are spatialised or lead to spatialisation (Simmel 1992; for a historical methodology: Rau 2019). The constructivist principle that spaces do not already exist but are created first also points in that direction: a social situation, and thus also a conflict or an ambivalence, takes shape spatially. This can be formulated in analogy to Simmel's famous sentence on the border: "The border is not a

spatial fact with sociological effects, but a sociological fact that takes shape spatially.”⁶ That said, we have to concede that once borders have been set, they also influence our thinking and acting. The same applies to other spatial configurations.

In this context, the concept of spatialisation is useful to focus on processes that can be triggered as a result of urban ambivalences, although they do not occur exclusively in such contexts (cf. Christ’s 2022 brief discussion of the concept). The interweaving of spatial and temporal levels must always be taken into account – if only when we consider the duration of spatialisation processes. After all, urbanity generally finds its most visible expression in the materialised result of a process of spatial temporalisation (*Verzeitlichung*), i.e. in an architectural form – be it a house, a square, a settlement or a more complex spatial configuration. What is more, the whole process of urbanisation, from this point of view, can be seen as spatialisation of an always particular, i.e. historically and culturally conditioned, society. The materialised, visible results or built spaces are admittedly only variants, perhaps the extreme ones, because they are most visible and show at the macro level. In what follows, we will deal with the various, by no means only, materialised, permanent forms of spatialisation that can arise from ambivalent situations. If we propose to assume that many social processes or urban ambivalences are spatialised, we should also consider the possibility that they may dissolve their spatial structure, or that their spatial practices may cease, that symbols to mark places lose their meaning.

Social relations range from couple or friendship relationships to associations, neighbourhoods and other social groups to relational dynamics among urban populations as a whole and to international relations between nations. The processes themselves can be transversal, but always relate back to the practices and activities of social actors or also to non-human actors of the wider environment or the imagined world. Here, the actors no longer control the processes (alone), but can at least still observe them.

Ambivalent states can endure in different forms of co-existence for long periods. However, whenever when they turn into tensions or conflicts (which often serve as catalysts for development) spatial arrangements become salient. Conflict resolution and conflict strategies can also become spatialised – however, not only in different ‘spatial’ ways. It is important to meaningfully distinguish the ambivalences that manifest

⁶ <https://socio.ch/sim/verschiedenes/1903/raum.htm> - in German: „Die Grenze ist nicht eine räumliche Tatsache mit soziologischen Wirkungen, sondern eine soziologische Tatsache, die sich räumlich formt.“

themselves in conflicts, states of tension or solution strategies: Ideally, one could distinguish between the spatialisation of

(a) short-term and long-lasting conflicts, such as the conflictual coexistence of Christians, Jews and Muslims in Beirut, Belfast or Jerusalem where latent conflicts, particularly during religious festivals or other open-air events in the urban space, have repeatedly led to acts of collective violence (Albrecht 2024);

(b) regulated, negotiated conflicts for which a more or less stable spatial solution was already found, such as with division and sharing of churches in some early modern European (imperial) cities where Christian groups of different denominations shared their churches either spatially or temporally;⁷ or the much more stabilised coexistence of Hindus, Muslims, Christians and Zoroastrians in Calicut (Narayanan 2018; Rau 2022; Rau/Muhammedali forthcoming#)

(c) ambivalences or conflicts that have not yet been resolved at all, but in which only one group or one party finds a solution for itself, which could then be described as claims for or occupations of space. A recent example would be Ayodhya in north-eastern India, a city that has been attributed religious significance by two different religious groups over centuries and where Hindu nationalists destroyed the architectural complex of Babri Masjid in 1992 and appropriated the place (Kulke 1994; Jobani and Perez 2020). Other cases can be found in the context of resettlement or gentrification processes, where parts of the urban population are forced to move due to official orders, because they can no longer afford the prices or, sooner or later, decide to leave due to loss of a sense of belonging.

However, spatialisation as a stabiliser of tensions or as a conflict strategy does not always express itself architecturally, but in many cases also symbolically: by placing flags or crosses, by singing or praying, by placing wooden or stone statues of gods, by keeping doors open or closed. We also know of cases in history where certain groups (often those treated as religious minorities) had to move to the suburbs or leave for good: such as the small group of Catholics, Mennonites or Jews in 17th and 18th century Hamburg who had their chapels or praying houses in Altona, or the protestants in Lyon who had to quit their small temples in the city centre and go to Oullins and later to a place in the Monts d'Or

⁷ Instead of a bibliography see the Website of the "Shared Churches"-project led by David M. Luebke, Marjorie E. Plummer and Andrew Spicer: <https://sharedchurches.arizona.edu/> (08.05.2025).

(Rau 2014: 156-159). Some of the 'lower castes' in historical Indian cities weren't even allowed to live in the cities but had to settle in a certain distance to the city. However, when groups were banned from the city (even if only to perform religious services), they leave traces in the city that can be destroyed, built over or forgotten – but also being rediscovered, like the old Jewish synagogue from the 11th century a few years ago, for which the city of Erfurt was awarded the UNESCO World Heritage title in September 2023.⁸ Thus, many forms of spatialisation are often not final or permanent but allow groups to spontaneously change the situation again at a later date, in one way or another – up to and including renewed destabilisation as a result of shifts in power. In the same way, objects and meanings can be 'taken away' or occupied spaces can be abandoned and neutralised.

This leads to the final aspect of spatialisation processes mentioned above. Assuming that many social processes or urban ambivalences are spatialised or expressed in spatial forms, we should also consider the possibility that they can dissolve their spatial form. Like production processes, dissolution is a temporal process, by no means always smooth, but sometimes quite abrupt. This dissolution does not always mean that the ambivalence – open or stabilized – disappeared from the battleground (let us think of the confessionally shared spaces); it can also be a sign that another solution has been found, for example a legal one that does not require a spatial or a spatiotemporal solution. Or it may mean that the tension has shifted to other areas, including virtual and digital worlds, if we approach to today's societies. As stated earlier (see chap. 3.2.1), this also includes our realization that there are degrees of belonging to a city.

It is usually a combination of social (and other) factors that contribute to the emergence of urban ambivalences. Returning to Simmel's sociology of boundaries and of space quoted at the beginning, we could argue, by analogy, that this ambivalence is not a spatial fact, but a sociological fact that takes shape spatially.

3.2.3 Individualisation and group formation

If the diagnosis of a core ambivalence of urbanity provides a key to understanding people's relationships, it needs to be spelt out in a third area. Nowhere else is the interplay

⁸ <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/1656/> (23.04.2024)

of the structural and subjective dimensions of urban ambivalence as visible as in religious individualization and group formation. In a structural perspective, cities were often articulated through religious symbols and a centripetal urbanity. Both stressed integration and supported belonging across all echelons of the urban society. This was performed via religious mass rituals, which enabled a multitude to participate at least in the role of spectators. At the same time, cities were centres of religious diversity long before the rise of organized religious groups, that is, they were spaces of religious action addressed to deities diverse in imagination, name, geographical origin, even language of communication. Such practices and imaginations, whether of ancestral or localized “powers”, shared by some people, offered the basis for feelings of belonging, created networks, and occasionally led to the formations of organized groups. Such genealogical figures (“ancestors”) or powers localized within the settlement or assumed to be based somewhere else (like in distant Jerusalem or Mekka, see Rüpke 2016b) were mediating or competing with each other regarding the attachment to the place and self-ascription to the city or inscription into the body of fully entitled citizens. Thus, a further prominent kind of tension was produced that intersected with other phenomena of the core ambivalence as sketched in 3.2.1 and often stabilized in spatialisations as sketched in 3.2.2. On the one hand, the size and diversity of the city could instigate processes of group formation that resulted in secondary groups, that is, networks or at least initially voluntary associations, catering for sociality, professional recognition, burial, and memorialisation. On the other hand, the complexity of urban interaction, overlapping networks, group memberships, and demands for social interaction, allowed individuals to define their selves in difference to all such groupings, that is, furthered an individualization that could buffer the super-sociality (see Woolf 2020) or even ultra-sociality of the city (Gowdy 2021).

Although seen as hallmarks of contemporary, and in particular “global”, cities (Becker et al. 2014; Garbin/Strhan 2017; Lanz 2018; Correia 2021), the formation of organized religious groups can be traced back for more than two millennia, e.g., into Mediterranean antiquity. Associations that were based primarily on voluntary membership (*collegia*, *thaisoi*) were present in ancient Mediterranean cities from early on in the urbanisation process (Rüpke 2018a). They gained increasing importance, particularly in the imperial era, as organisational forms for religious group formation and as important actors in urban social life and its architecture (Hemelrijk 2008, Rohde 2012, Eckhardt, Leonhard

2018, Kloppenborg 2019, Last 201). *Collegia* were private organisations that could acquire a legal status and ownership by registering. The range of different types of associations has remained very broad to this day: in ancient Rome, the slaves of a large household (*familia*) could join together to form a collegium, down into early modern Rome, ethnic groups of immigrant could do so (e.g., Carroll 2017). Self-employed craftsmen joined together to form large professional associations, and they did so in religious rituals as also witnessed in late medieval European towns (Oexle 1985, Stollberg-Rilinger 2019, Rau 2021). They did this partly for sociable purposes, but also to protect their rights and status, as was the case with the medieval guilds in Europe. And quite often, the primary purpose was a religious one, the worship of a deity or a saint, leading to the establishment of a deliberately religious group. The name of the association, the place or built-up space of the meeting or a founding ritual then allowed members and observers to ascribe religious identities to themselves respectively these people (see Keune 2021, for today's Western India). In ancient Mediterranean cities, the sphere of influence was primarily local, and the number of members allowed face-to-face encounters between a dozen and not significantly more than a hundred members. Eating together was the community-building ritual par excellence, providing food could extend this in a hierarchical manner (thus creating inclusion and exclusion at the same time). It was such groups and a process of trying to integrate them into a local clerical hierarchy that late ancient urban Christianities formed (Leppin 2018; Rüpke 2018b; Lätzer-Lasar/Urciuoli 2021; Schliesser 2021; Maier 2024). Such larger groups could compete with a semantics and rituals of a local "civic religion" (ancient) or (as diagnosed in the 20th century) "civil religion" stressing political integration, or could be subsidiary to politically and elite-driven religious symbolisations of urban identity. Historically, religious monopoly was a goal particularly in those cases, where legitimation of power was primarily religious. In the face of religiously defined minorities or powerful competitors this could be a major source of urban unrest and violence (in general, Makrides/Rüpke/Kasten 2005; Buc 2010; Kong/Woods 2016; Winter 2020, Mersch 2022; Riva 2022; Albrecht 2024) as the medieval and early modern history of European cities that were not able to permanently tolerate Jews or post-Reformation pluralization demonstrates (Rubin 2020, 2021; Reformation: Dunwoody 2013; Ozment/Eire/Rittgers 2020; Christ 2021).

The latter story is well-known. However, the focus on ambivalence opens a perspective on tensions beyond Europe and the late-medieval and early modern period regarding modalities of group formation and the strive for individuality or “individualisation”. Regarding individualization research had long been obstructed by the close linkage of individualism and Western modernity that excluded possibilities and trajectories of individualization in other parts of the world and before ‘modernity’. As a focus on individualization has played only a limited role in the examination of the dynamics of religion in history, the ambivalence of premodern urban societies and religion in such frameworks had been overlooked. It had been a great effort of a recent comparative research group to open the view for the multiple modes of individualization in ‘pre-modern’ times in the world at large (Fuchs et al. 2019). Examples show that urban socio-spatial configurations opened space for individuality in several dimension, not least the religious. Individualization comprises high degrees of diversity and of division of labour as condition that do not only allow for but shape very different processes of socialization and biographies. A discourse favouring individual distinction and competition or even affirming individual choice and responsibilities (or even rights) often accompanied such socio-structural differentiation and became part of urbanity. Such individualization and its individual articulations could take very different forms, even in the realm of religious practices. This could range from distinction by excelling in religious lavishness, for instance by financing the monumentalization or decoration of commonly used religious space, through intensified religious practices and asceticism to individualized world views and de-traditionalized practices (ibid.). Whether this was seen by the historical actors as “exotic” (and maybe attractive) or attacked as deviant was a matter of circumstances and visibility (Rüpke 2016a).

One of the instruments of such developments of a specific and individualized subjectivity leading to specifically religious forms of belonging for numerous people was writing, a medium characteristic of cities into the modern era (Law et al. 2015). The availability of durable and movable carriers of written thought allowed professional scribes in ancient Mesopotamian cities, Jewish prophets and other “intellectuals” of the Hellenistic and Roman age and in the Indian subcontinent from the late first millennium BCE onwards to reflect on their individual relationship to the world (and their cities). This included ascetic movements that were central to Jainism, Buddhism and Christianity. It comprised imagining relationships to specific and imaginable deities in forms of prophecy,

narratives, or poems – or to simply express and conceptualize devotion to a particular deity by the wording of a dedication accompanied by an inscription (Beard 1991; Krueger 2004; Toorn 2008; Haines-Eitzen 2012; Keegan 2013; Goossaert 2015; Belayche 2018; Anthonioz 2019). This allowed religious individualization embedded in forms of prophetic claims to be the chosen ones (in Tenakh prophets, foundational Islam or medieval and modern Christianities) or in mysticism (from Jewish Kabbalah and Hasidism through Islamic *sūfis* to European monastic mystics). In all these cases such textual production (and usage) went hand in hand with concepts of individual authorship that made such individuality visible. At the same time, the continuous presence of such texts allowed for establishing bonds between readers or interpreters (Stock 1983); recitations in front of an audience provided contents of communication and imaginations of belonging that helped to stabilize groups. For India, writing in the context of urban manifestations of *bhakti* exemplifies this whole range of possibilities. The narrative and theological framework of the written propagation of an individual and even loving relationship between a human and a god—Krishna, Ram and Shiva being particularly popular, wherever the addressee was regarded as personalized (*saguna*) – or with the Supreme as non-personalized (*nirguna*), like in the case of Kabir, proved to be a reservoir that led and leads to processes of individualization of very different forms. These are different in terms of the media employed and the longevity of the process (Eck/Mallison 1991). They could serve as a medium of expression, for instance in giving a voice to women in the form of religious poetry and thus constituting a self (Chakravarty 1989; Craddock 2007). Its inbuilt distancing from the world as it is and simultaneous opening towards divine and human others could serve as political tool and basis for political movements, which aimed at gaining recognition (Fuchs 2001, 2019; Omvedt 2008) and could add to urban tensions.

Religious individualisation built on urban techniques like writing and reading were bolstered by the formation of groups that vowed to support such individual choice. Cross-culturally, however, such religious groups often start controlling and regulating individual behaviour in a manner that can be seen as paradoxical (e.g. Rebillard, Rüpke 2015) or as expression of the fundamental ambivalence diagnosed above. Groups that heavily invested in practices of writing and reading could remove themselves from urban spaces and transferred urban techniques and urban mind-sets, urbanity, into the hinterland of cities in the form of monasteries (Rüpke/Urciuoli 2023). Yet, urban socio-

spatial relations and communication in such configurations remained primary seedbeds and intensifiers for these processes, offering points of attachment to existing networks or shelters for deviant behaviour. Illustrating the ambivalence of the urban as well as the religious, interests in regulating and standardizing urban behaviour and the concentration of social power and control of knowledge turned cities into centres of organized suppression not least furthered by religion. Religious plurality, confessional strife and exclusion of those classified (on whatever criterion) as “others” have been closely connected if seen through the lens of ambivalence.

4 Conclusion

As we have shown the concept of ambivalence can be fruitfully used for analysing urban socio-spatial relations and configurations. Ambivalence is not just a metaphor for complexity. Instead, identifying a core ambivalence of the urban offers to precisely capture underlying tensions in cities of different epochs, on different continents, and of very different religious constellations. Thus, we suggest this as an important instrument for any comparative study of urban strains. In particular, this instrument allows to investigate the reciprocal formation of urbanity and religion and its many tensions. As we have indicated above (2.2), religion itself can also be fruitfully analysed through the lens of ambivalence. However, the ambivalences for religious practices and beliefs hinted at are very different. Yet, wherever religion and urbanity reciprocally shape each other, the ambivalences at the core of both will have been and will continue to be decisive factors in/of this entanglement. One might use this to better understand the complexity and vast differences that we see at work in urban-religious trajectories in urban settlements and urban thinking across periods and regions. Identifying ambivalence in both dimensions sheds light on the large variety of local and trans-regional urban constellations. We suggest accepting and embracing the complexity of the double ambivalence as a complex model for historical and comparative analyses that are interested in the nuances of similarities and differences without losing sight of the advantages of overarching concepts. It is for this aim that we intend to further develop the ambivalence of religious socio-spatial relations and configurations.

In this article, we focussed on the urban side. Looking at urban ambivalences lays open the inherent frailty of the urban way of life. Despite the repeated growth of urbanism in many epochs and regions and despite the ongoing process that has been called planetary urbanisation (Brenner 2014; Brenner, Schmid 2014), the urban remains a precarious form of humans' living together. Focusing on urban strain in such a manner foregrounds the volatile balance and the enormous energy put into attaining at least temporarily a state of stability for large scale, urban settlements (Rehberg 2014). This is the core tension of settlements that grow beyond what might be the limits of meaningful face-to-face interaction and whose residents emphatically embrace these possibilities and reflect this as urbanity. Under these conditions, the questions of inclusion and exclusion, or as we foregrounded, of belonging, become a constitutive concern in many forms of urban strain. The concept of ambivalence, as the review of the history of the concept has made clear, is not about situational disputes or political divides. It is about co-existing and enduring powerful normative alternatives. Dealing with these tensions means going into the heart of urban projects beyond all other contingent sources of urban strain.

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